

The role of artificial intelligence in promoting university students' psychological well-being: State of the art and future perspectives

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University life exposes students to considerable academic pressure and a range of personal challenges that can compromise mental health, increasing the likelihood of psychological difficulties and potentially hindering both educational progress and future career development. Within this context, existing research consistently highlights the need for interventions that can anticipate emotional problems among university students and respond both effectively and promptly, allowing individuals to manage emerging crises before they escalate. In recent years, artificial intelligence has gained attention as a promising resource for predicting emotional difficulties among students and for delivering personalised support. AI systems can process information from multiple sources to detect early signs of distress, offering a level of immediacy and precision that traditional services often cannot provide. These developments have encouraged researchers to explore how AI might help universities offer more accessible and responsive mental health support. Accordingly, this brief report reviews empirical and applied studies examining the use of AI tools such as chatbots, emotion recognition systems, and wearable technologies to support the psychological well-being of university students. The aim is to identify which technologies appear most effective, to clarify current opportunities and limitations, and to outline directions for future research.

Keywords: artificial intelligence; emotion recognition; mental health; university students; wearable technologies

According to recent research (e.g., Xiang et al., 2024), mental health plays a crucial role in influencing the academic performance of university students. Indeed, empirical studies suggest that university life is often burdened with anxiety, pressure, stress, and challenges that can negatively impact psychological and physical well-being: psychologically, by promoting the onset of internalising problems such as anxiety, depression, social withdrawal, and sleep problems (Shahzad et al., 2024); biologically, by negatively impacting physical health with an increased likelihood of developing heart disease, gastrointestinal problems, and blood pressure problems; and academically, by negatively impacting academic performance (e.g., Xiang et al., 2024). To respond to this emergency, in recent years, there has been a growing need to create algorithms and models that leverage Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the big data used to predict potential emotional crises among students (Lei et al., 2023).

In this framework, AI can identify behavioural and emotional variations through the continuous analysis of real-time data (e.g., Bromuri et al., 2021). Specifically, by processing several inputs, such as linguistic patterns, physical indicators, emotional facial expressions, and vocal tone, AI tools can precisely detect an individual's affective state that is difficult to detect by a human observer, based on the integration of inputs from different sources of information (Lazarides & Chevalère, 2021; Liu, 2024). This capability enables the implementation of highly personalised interventions that surpass the limitations of traditional counselling and therapeutic services, often constrained by time and accessibility, which obstruct their ability to provide continuous and individualised support (Jiang et al., 2024). In fact, unlike traditional interventions such as psychotherapy and counselling, AI tools have several advantages, such as the opportunity to have continuous support, the cost-effective monitoring of students' emotional well-being, and the capability to detect emotional problems early (Liu, 2024; Zhao et al., 2024).

According to these premises, this brief report aims to summarise the state of the art of international studies and research that have leveraged artificial intelligence to create tools to support the mental health of university students, preventing potential emotional crises and providing appropriate and personalised treatment for managing any issues (Liu, 2024; Zhao et al., 2024). To achieve this goal, we examined empirical and applied studies published between 2017 and 2024, identified through Scopus and PubMed searches using combinations of the following keywords: “artificial intelligence”, “university students”, and “mental health”.

Artificial intelligence and university students' mental health

Several studies have attempted to harness the potential of artificial intelligence to support mental health among university students (Lazarides & Chevalère, 2021). A significant contribution is made by Shahzad and colleagues (2024), who implemented an intelligent mental health support system to help students understand and better manage their emotional state. Specifically, the system provides detailed reports on students' psychological adjustment based on self-report questionnaires (Shahzad et al., 2024). It gives corresponding suggestions to help users better understand their mental health status and promptly identify and resolve potential psychological problems (Shahzad et al., 2024). The authors therefore created a self-help mental health platform, enabling students to understand their psychological state and receive relevant advice for managing potential emotional crises, with the assistance of online psychologists (Mousavi Baigi et al., 2023). The system's technical framework (based on Java EE and a weighted inference model) enables rapid detection of abnormal emotional responses, improving students' self-awareness and access to mental health support (Shahzad et al., 2024). The system, therefore, uses weighted reasoning on the information provided by students to diagnose potential psychological problems and provide corresponding solutions (Mousavi Baigi et al., 2023).

Still, about mental health, there are numerous applications of artificial intelligence and machine learning for promoting psychological well-being, prevention, diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment of various psychopathologies (Dwyer et al., 2018). Early machine learning studies have demonstrated how diagnoses applied to single individuals could be somewhat replicated in large data structures (Arbabshirani et al., 2017). Following this direction, recent empirical research showed that chatbot-

based psychological interventions demonstrate high levels of user acceptance, particularly among university student samples (Gong, 2021; Mousavi Baigi et al., 2023). Chatbots are digital agents designed to simulate elements of therapeutic dialogue (Gong, 2021). They have been shown to promote university students' mental health by reducing symptoms of anxiety and stress (Jiang et al., 2024). In this context, Elomia (Romanovskyi et al., 2021) is a chatbot designed to identify users' main psychological problems and offer the most suitable support options, using mainly cognitive behavioural psychotherapy techniques. Specifically, Elomia includes calming exercises, sleep exercises, exercises to reduce anxiety, breathing exercises, and exercises to improve self-esteem (Romanovskyi et al., 2021). Elomia is based on an algorithm that determines the user's need for communication with the chatbot and suggests an exercise to alleviate/regulate their emotional state (Romanovskyi et al., 2021).

Following the direction of these studies, it could be beneficial to develop a system that integrates the probabilistic AHP approach with a chatbot to assess the likelihood of an emotional crisis and assist university students in preventing and, if necessary, autonomously managing the crisis and stress through the provision of cognitive-behavioural exercises (Lazarides & Chevalère, 2021). However, the most significant limitation of artificial intelligence must be considered: the lack of a proper understanding of human emotional life (e.g., Oberiri, 2019). In this sense, future projects could benefit from developing systems that can objectively recognise emotions, particularly given their crucial importance for mental health (Izard, 2013).

Artificial intelligence to detect university students' emotional state

Among the tools for assessing emotions that use artificial intelligence systems, SERMO (Denecke et al., 2020) stands out. It is a mobile application that integrates a chatbot with cognitive behavioural therapy techniques to help manage and regulate emotions (Denecke et al., 2020). SERMO uses the ecological momentary assessment method (EMA, Wen et al., 2017; an innovative methodology that allows for the measurement of variables in their natural context) through daily questions to which the user responds, relating to emotions and events, to identify basic emotions using natural language. However, a limitation of this tool is that, despite the advantages of daily emotion assessment from an ecological perspective, it would be helpful for a correct assessment of emotions to use objective indicators of the emotion experienced by the user (Mitsea et al., 2023).

In this direction, several contributions have been developed in recent years based on facial expressions, which are important objective indicators of emotions (Lewis et al., 2008). For example, Saxena and colleagues (2020) have utilised artificial intelligence to develop systems that detect basic emotions in both real-time and static images. The target expression for each sequence in the datasets is fully encoded by the FACS (Facial Action Coding System; Ekman et al., 2002). Therefore, for emotion recognition, faces are initially detected, after which the face can be cropped and processed for further facial landmark detection (Saxena et al., 2020). Then, using the facial landmarks, the datasets are trained using a machine learning algorithm (i.e., Support Vector Machine) and then classified according to primary emotions (i.e., anger, sadness, fear, disgust, contempt, surprise, joy), achieving an accuracy of approximately 93.7% (Saxena et al., 2020). Additional methods can be employed for emotion detection, including the recognition of physiological signals, vocal signal variations, and text semantics (e.g., Calzolari et al., 2025). However, recent meta-analyses suggest that studying facial expressions of emotion is the most reliable method (e.g., Ko, 2018).

In this sense, the EMA allows a higher ecological validity, considering that variables are measured in the real daily context in which they happen, while physiological and facial recognition methods offer objective accuracy but are not necessarily measured in real-time (Depp et al., 2022). This method could be useful to integrate these approaches to afford a better understanding of students' emotional dynamics (Mitsea et al., 2023; Relojo et al., 2015).

Another recent study, conducted by Ballesteros and colleagues (2024), utilised artificial intelligence (AI) to apply computer vision algorithms to detect human emotions in video content during user interactions with various visual stimuli. The authors' research laid the foundation for the

development of software capable of detecting emotions using AI algorithms and identifying users' facial expressions (Ballesteros et al., 2024). The process involves assessing users through images and facilitating the implementation of computer vision algorithms aligned with psychological theories that define emotions and their recognisable characteristics (Depp et al., 2022). The study demonstrates the feasibility of emotion recognition using convolutional neural networks (CNNs), a type of artificial neural network designed to analyse visual images, and the development and training of facial expression-based software (Ballesteros et al., 2024). The results highlight the success of emotion identification; however, it is essential to enhance the accuracy of emotion detection to enable the identification of more complex emotions beyond primary ones and to integrate this approach with implications for the provision of emotion regulation strategies (Depp et al., 2022). Finally, it is important to acknowledge that, despite the relevant insights about emotion recognition studies; these are often limited in terms of demographic variability, which may reduce the accuracy of emotion recognition across populations with different socio-demographic characteristics (Mitsea et al., 2023).

Smart wearable devices and mental health

In recent years, the use of smart wearable devices has become increasingly widespread, aiming to promote physical health through the monitoring and analysis of data obtained based on physiological and behavioural indicators (Wortley et al., 2017).

There are numerous current applications for these devices, which, synchronised with a mobile device such as a smartphone, allow users to view collected data and monitor progress, particularly (but not limited to) for physical activity, and increasingly monitoring data related to physical health, such as heart rate, sleep, weight, and blood pressure (Zhao et al., 2024). Along these lines, Long and colleagues (2022) suggest that smart sensors can accurately detect subtle changes (such as insomnia, headaches, rapid heart rate, and muscle tension) in the body caused by stress, thereby preventing and reducing the adverse effects of mental health problems on physical well-being. In particular, the most widespread applications include measuring electroencephalography (EEG), electrocardiography (ECG), and electrodermal activity (EDA) in healthy adults using wearable devices and artificial intelligence algorithms to predict potential psychological issues with implications for holistic well-being (Long et al., 2022).

In this regard, algorithms that utilise Big Data and artificial intelligence in wearable intelligent technologies (Gaffar & Gearhart, 2024) have achieved positive results, particularly in physical health. However, concerning mental health, most studies, despite using mobile applications with chatbots integrated with cognitive behavioural therapy methods to manage and regulate emotions and behaviour (Jiang et al., 2024), only rarely use wearable devices and integrate data from different objective sources (e.g., physiological indicators, semantic indicators, facial expressions of emotions) to promote holistic well-being. Furthermore, most of the wearable-based studies have been conducted with general adult populations, and only a few (such as Long et al., 2022) have directly examined university students. This aspect suggests the need to validate these tools among university students as well.

CONCLUSION

Despite the widespread proliferation of tools that utilise artificial intelligence to promote the psychological well-being of university students, several limitations remain. Among these, a significant limitation is that the tools described often fail to integrate various objective indicators to predict stress or emotional dysregulation and are often difficult to access (Mitsea et al., 2023). It is necessary to go beyond these limitations by creating systems capable of integrating objective information for emotion recognition using multiple sources (e.g., physiological indicators, semantic indicators) and leveraging the ecological validity of daily assessment, such as EMA (e.g., Depp et al., 2022). This should not be limited to identifying primary (universal) emotions, but also secondary emotions, unique to humans, which are closely related to psychopathology and have scarcely been examined in previous studies (i.e., anxiety, embarrassment, shame, guilt; Izard, 2013). This should enable the probabilistic calculation of an emotional crisis and the provision of appropriate cognitive-

behavioural support through integrated chatbot systems (Shahzad et al., 2024). In this sense, it would also be beneficial to leverage the potential of wearable smart devices, such as smartwatches, smart glasses, or smart rings, to monitor various indicators of psychological well-being continuously (Mascia et al., 2024).

Future research, therefore, faces the challenge of harnessing the high potential of artificial intelligence to create tools that are accessible to all and can constantly monitor the emotional state of university students through objective indicators (Ballesteros et al., 2024). These indicators allow for monitoring not only primary emotions (fear, anger, disgust, sadness, contempt, happiness, surprise) but also secondary emotions (anxiety, embarrassment, shame, guilt; Calzolari et al., 2025). This is achieved through facial expression recognition (based on the FACS; facial action coding system) combined with physiological indicators such as salivary cortisol levels measured upon awakening (an indicator of stress, a key factor in emotional crisis), and semantic indicators (e.g., vocal tone) daily (ecological momentary assessment). These indicators are used to calculate the risk of a potential emotional crisis (AHP algorithm) and provide cognitive-behavioural exercises via chatbots to enable students to manage/regulate emotions and stress autonomously (Depp et al., 2022). This would have important implications for the prevention of mental health problems in university students, particularly given the serious risks that such problems pose to both individual and collective well-being (Lazarides & Chevalère, 2021; Liu, 2024). In conclusion, based on the reviewed studies, future research should integrate ecological momentary assessment with wearable sensors and chatbot agents to provide continuous and personalised support for university students' mental health that is more sustainable and accessible.

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